

Half-sandwich η^6 -benzene ruthenium(II) complexes of phenolate-based 2-(pyridyl)alkylamine and bis-pyrazole ligands: Synthesis, spectra, structure and non-covalent interactions

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Two new half-sandwich complexes $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**), supported by two mononegative phenolate-based ligands ($\text{L}^6 = [2,6\text{-bis}(\text{pyrazol-1-ylmethyl})\text{-4-methylphenol}]$ and $\text{L}^{10} = 6\text{-}\{[2'\text{-}((\text{pyridin-2-yl})\text{benzylamino})\text{methyl}]\text{-phenol}$) are synthesized and structurally characterized. ^1H NMR spectral measurements have been done to investigate the structure in solution. Analysis of crystal-packing of **1** and **2** reveals the presence of $\text{C-H}\cdots\text{O}$ and $\text{C-H}\cdots\pi$ non-covalent interactions.

Keywords: Phenolate-based ligands with 2-(pyridyl)methylamine and pyrazol-1-ylmethyl arms, $\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6$ -coordinated half-sandwich ruthenium(II) complexes, crystal structures, ^1H NMR spectra, non-covalent interactions.

Introduction

Arene ruthenium compounds belong to a well-established family of robust organometallic molecules¹. Continued interest in such systems arises due to their catalytic potential in a wide range of organic reactions^{2,3}, DNA binding⁴, very promising anticancer activity⁵⁻⁷ of $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{en})\text{Cl}]^+$ ($\text{en} = 1,2\text{-diaminoethane}$) class of complexes and supramolecular chemistry⁸. These findings provide the impetus for the synthesis⁹⁻¹¹ and study the reactivity¹² properties of new $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}/\text{L}')\}^{2+}$ (L is bidentate and L' is tridentate neutral N-donor ligand) complexes.

During our investigations into the chemistry of half-sandwich three-legged 'piano-stool' complexes of ruthenium(II) having $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\}^{2+}$ moiety^{10,11}, we utilized a series of bidentate/tridentate pyridine-based N-donor ligands (Fig. 1) to study bridge-cleavage reactions on $\{[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{Cl}]_2\}$. In the chosen ligands, between the two donor sites there exists a spacer ($-\text{CH}_2-$ or $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$). We synthesized and structurally characterized, most of the complexes, with tridentate (2-pyridyl)alkylamine ligand $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^1)](\text{PF}_6)_2$ ^{10a}, with bidentate nonplanar pyrazolymethylpyridine ligands $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^2)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ (a dangling pyrazole arm)^{10a}, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^3)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ (a dangling 3,5-dimethylpyrazole arm)^{10a}, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^4)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ ^{10a,c}, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^4)\text{N}_3](\text{PF}_6)$ ^{10c}, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{4*})\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$

$(\text{L}^{4*} = 2\text{-}[3\text{-}(4\text{-chlorophenyl})\text{pyrazol-1-ylmethyl}]\text{pyridine})$ ^{10b} and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{4**})\text{N}_3](\text{PF}_6)\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3$ ($\text{L}^{4**} = 2\text{-}[3\text{-}(4\text{-fluorophenyl})\text{pyrazol-1-ylmethyl}]\text{pyridine})$ ^{10c}. It should be mentioned here that $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^2)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ ^{10a} and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^3)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ ^{10a} were not structurally characterized. We also synthesized and structurally characterized similar complexes with composition $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^*)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ ^{10c} supported by bidentate N-donor ligands having directly attached two heterocycles ($\text{HL}^* = 3\text{-}(2\text{-pyridyl})\text{pyrazole}/1\text{-benzyl-}[3\text{-}(2'\text{-pyridyl})\text{pyrazole}/2\text{-}(1\text{-imidazol-2-yl})\text{pyridine}]$ ^{10c}).

Although several examples of structurally characterized mononuclear three-legged 'piano-stool' half-sandwich organometallic complexes having $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\}^{2+}$ unit supported by neutral N-donor ligands are known^{9,10}, the number of Ru^{II} -arene complexes with anionic ligands in general are limited^{2d,3d,g,i,13} and phenol-based ligands are scarce^{3d,g,11,13a,b}. From the standpoint of synthetic chemistry we find it really challenging.

By introducing a *p*-methylphenol donor group in place of a pyridine in ligand L^2 (two five-membered chelate rings), which acts as a bidentate ligand in $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^2)\text{Cl}](\text{PF}_6)$ ^{10a} with a dangling pyrazole arm (Fig. 1), it is expected to provide more flexibility (two seven-membered chelate rings) to the coordination of deprotonated ligand $\text{L}^6(-)$. In that case, there is a possibility that the new ligand $\text{L}^6(-)$ can adopt fa-

Fig. 1. The ligands of pertinence to this work.

cial coordination mode of binding, utilizing all the three donor sites. The ligand HL^6 is of interest for another reason. In the case of reported copper(II)^{14a} and zinc(II)^{14b} complexes the $L^6(-)$ coordinates as a bridging-bidentate ligand giving rise to $\{M^{II}_2(\mu\text{-phenoxo})_2\}^{2+}$ complexes. To provide examples of $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{II}\}^{2+}$ complexes with non-Schiff base phenolate-based chelating ligands in this study we have synthesized $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{II}(L^6)\}(\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{II}(L^{10})\}(\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**). We are not aware of any structurally characterized arene-ruthenium complex of tridentate uninegative bis(pyrazole)phenol ligand and non-Schiff base phenol/(2-pyridyl)alkylamine-hybrid chelating ligand. Thus the present work demands attention. Herein we describe the synthesis and structural characterization (crystal structure and ¹H NMR spectral properties) of **1** and **2**. The tridentate phenol-based ligand HL^{10} has been chosen as an extension of our previous work¹¹, where we reported $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{II}(L^9)\text{Cl}\}(\text{PF}_6)$ ¹¹. Here we wish to test the electronic effect of unsubstituted phenolate-based (2-pyridyl)alkylamine ligand on the strength

of $\text{Ru}^{II}\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6$ bonding. Due to larger size, geometrical requirement of the piano-stool complex with $L^6(-)$ and coordination flexibility, $L^6(-)$ acts as a tridentate ligand in **1**. Here we wish to test the electronic effect of unsubstituted phenolate-based (2-pyridyl)alkylamine ligand on the strength of $\text{Ru}^{II}\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6$ bonding.

Experimental

Materials:

Reagent or analytical grade starting materials were obtained from commercial sources and used without further purification. The starting dimer $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{II}\text{Cl}(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2$ ¹⁵, [2,6-bis((pyrazol-1-yl)methyl)-4-methylphenol (HL^6)^{14a} and 2-[(pyridin-2-ylmethylamino)methyl]phenol (HL^{10})¹⁶ were synthesized following literature procedures.

Synthesis of complexes:

$\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(L^6)\}(\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**): The ligand HL^6 (0.107 g, 0.4 mmol) and triethylamine (0.04 g, 0.4 mmol) were dissolved in MeOH (15 mL) and to it solid $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{RuCl}(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2$ (0.1 g, 0.2 mmol) was added. The mixture was stirred for 8 h at 298 K. The resulting brown yellow solution was filtered through a celite pad and the volume of the filtrate was reduced to ~7 mL and to it solid NH_4PF_6 (0.065 g, 0.4 mmol) was added. The yellow microcrystalline solid that formed was filtered, washed with a mixture of diethyl ether and MeOH (1:1, v/v) and dried *in vacuo*. Recrystallization was achieved from MeCN/diethyl ether. X-Ray quality single-crystals were obtained by diffusion of diethyl ether into a solution (1 mL) of the complex in a mixture (1:1, v/v) of MeOH and MeCN. Yield: 0.120 g (50%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_4\text{F}_6\text{OPRu}$: C, 42.65; H, 3.58; N, 9.47. Found: C, 42.54; H, 3.54; N, 9.41; ¹H NMR (CD_3CN ; 400 MHz; 298 K): δ 8.16 (d, $J_{\text{HH}} = 2.1$ Hz, 2H, H_5 of pz), 7.77 (d, $J_{\text{HH}} = 1.9$ Hz, 2H, H_3 of pz), 6.70 (s, 2H, $H_{3',5'}$ of PhO), 6.35 (t, $J_{\text{HH}} = 2.4$ Hz, 2H, H_4 of pz), 5.89 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 12.9$ Hz, 2H, CH_2 -), 5.76 (s, 6H, C_6H_6), 4.79 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 13.1$ Hz, 2H, CH_2 -), 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3 -); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 833 $\nu(\text{PF}_6^-)$; UV-Vis (in MeCN): λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) 420 sh (1070), 330 (3950), 245 (15950).

$\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(L^{10})\}(\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**): The method for the synthesis of **1** was followed, with HL^{10} (0.122 g, 0.4 mmol). Addition of diethylether (15 mL) afforded yellow solid which was filtered, washed with a mixture of diethyl ether and MeOH (3:1, v/v) and dried *in vacuo*. Recrystallization was achieved from MeCN/diethyl ether. Diffusion of diethyl ether into a MeCN solution afforded X-ray quality orange single-crystals.

The resulting yellow crystalline solid contains two isomers of the desired complex in the ratio 1:1, which can be distinguished by their ^1H NMR spectra (see below). Yield: 0.150 g (60%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_2\text{F}_6\text{OPRu}$: C, 49.76; H, 3.98; N, 4.46. Found: C, 49.59; H, 3.92; N, 4.51; ^1H NMR (CD_3CN ; 500 MHz; 233 K): δ 9.05 (d, $J_{\text{HH}} = 4.5$ Hz, 1H, $\text{H}_{6'}$ of py), 8.81 (d, $J_{\text{HH}} = 4.5$ Hz, 1H, $\text{H}_{6'}$ of py), 7.91 (t, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.7$ Hz, 1H, H_4 of py), 7.61–7.43 (m, 12H, H_4 of py, $\text{H}_{6'}$ of PhO, and $\text{H}_{2''} - \text{H}_{6''}$ of phenyl), 7.21 (m, 2H, $\text{H}_{6'}$ of PhO and H_5 of py), 7.04 (m, 2H, H_3 and H_5 of py), 6.75 (d, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.5$ Hz, 1H, H_3 of py), 6.70 (t, $J_{\text{HH}} = 6.7$ Hz, 1H, $\text{H}_{4'}$ of PhO), 6.57 (t, $J_{\text{HH}} = 6.7$ Hz, 1H, $\text{H}_{4'}$ of PhO), 6.27 (t, $J_{\text{HH}} = 6.5$ Hz, 1H, $\text{H}_{5'}$ of PhO), 6.15 (d, $J_{\text{HH}} = 7.5$ Hz, 1H, H_3' of PhO), 6.6.07 (t, $J_{\text{HH}} = 6.5$ Hz, 1H, $\text{H}_{5'}$ of PhO), 5.88 (s, 6H, C_6H_6), 5.72 (d,s, overlapped 7H, H_3' of PhO and C_6H_6), 5.36 (d, 2H, $J_{\text{gem}} = 14$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of pyridyl), 5.05 (d, 2H, $J_{\text{gem}} = 14$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of pyridyl), 4.57 (dd, $J_{\text{gem}}^1 = 14.5$ Hz, $J_{\text{gem}}^2 = 12.0$ Hz, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of PhO, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of PhO), 4.12 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 14.5$ Hz, 1H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of PhO), 3.69 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 12$ Hz, 1H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of benzyl), 3.60 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 13$ Hz, 1H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of PhO), 3.14 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 12$ Hz, 1H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of benzyl), 2.84 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 12$ Hz, 1H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of benzyl), 1.75 (d, $J_{\text{gem}} = 12$ Hz, 1H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of benzyl); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 834 $\nu(\text{PF}_6^-)$. UV-Vis (in MeCN): λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) 350 (4700), 306 sh (6800).

Physical measurements:

Elemental analyses were obtained using Thermo Quest EA 1110 CHNS-O, Italy. Spectroscopic measurements were made using the following instruments: IR (KBr, 4000–600 cm^{-1}), Bruker Vector 22; electronic, Perkin-Elmer Lambda 2 and Agilent 8453 diode-array spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectral measurements were performed on a JEOL-JNM-LA-400 FT (400 MHz) NMR spectrometer.

X-Ray crystallography:

Diffraction intensities were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer at 100(2) K using graphite-monochromated $\text{MoK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71069$ Å) radiation. Intensity data were corrected for Lorentz polarization effects. Empirical absorption correction (SADABS) was applied. The structures were solved by SIR-97, expanded by Fourier-difference syntheses, and refined with SHELXL-97, incorporated in WINGX 1.64 crystallographic collective package¹⁷. Hydrogen atoms were placed in idealized positions, and treated using riding model approximation with displacement parameters derived from those of the atoms to which they were bonded. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotro-

pic thermal parameters by full-matrix least-squares procedures on F^2 . A summary of the data collection and structure refinement information is provided in Table 1. Intermolecular contacts of the C–H...O, and C–H... π type were examined with the DIAMOND package¹⁸. C–H distances were normalized along the same vectors to the neutron derived value of 1.083 Å.

Table 1. Data collection and structure refinement parameters for $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**)

	1	2
Chemical formula	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OPF}_6\text{Ru}$	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{OPF}_6\text{Ru}$
M	591.46	625.50
Crystal colour, habit	Yellow, block	Orange, block
T (K)	100(2)	100(2)
Cryst system	Monoclinic	Trigonal
Space group	<i>Im</i>	<i>R</i> -3
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.3216(8)	33.4270(17)
<i>b</i> (Å)	10.4720(11)	33.4270(17)
<i>c</i> (Å)	14.6927(15)	11.6722(7)
α (°)	90	90
β (°)	101.761(2)	90
γ (°)	90	120
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1102.9(2)	11294.8(11)
Z	2	18
d_{calcd} (g cm^{-3})	1.781	1.655
μ (mm^{-1})	0.857	0.756
<i>F</i> (000)	592	5652
No. of reflns collected	3638	25353
No. of indep reflns [<i>R</i> (int)]	1938 [0.0316]	6250 [0.0593]
No. of reflns used [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	1862	4915
GOF on F^2	1.103	1.079
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0442, 0.0944	0.0461, 0.0974
Final <i>R</i> indices (all data)	0.0512, 0.1017	0.0697, 0.1192
$^a R_1 = \sum(F_o - F_c)/\sum F_o $. $^b wR_2 = \{\sum[w(F_o ^2 - F_c ^2)^2]/\sum[w(F_o)^2]\}^{1/2}$		

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization:

Bridge-cleavage reaction of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cl}]$ with HL^6 and HL^{10} in the presence of triethylamine in MeOH followed by treatment with NH_4PF_6 resulted in the isolation of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**), as microcrystalline solid. Characterization of **1** and **2** were accomplished by elemental analysis, IR and ^1H NMR spectra and by their crystal structures.

As proof of their orange to yellow colour, complexes **1**

and **2** exhibit absorption spectral band in the 350–420 nm region, due to (phenolate) \rightarrow Ru^{II} charge-transfer (LMCT) transition.

¹H NMR spectra:

¹H NMR spectroscopy provides easy means of characterization of these half-sandwich complexes. The data (CD₃CN; 298 K) along with their assignments are recorded in the Experimental section, supporting their expected 'piano-stool' structure. The spectral feature of **1** (Fig. 2) is consistent with the presence of a coordinated benzene ligand and a tridentate ligand L⁶(-). The proton resonances were assigned, based on available ¹H NMR spectral results for free ligand (HL⁶)¹⁴ and closely similar half-sandwich complexes¹⁰. The chemical shift values for coordinated benzene in **1** is δ 5.75. An AB quartet for CH₂ protons of L⁶(-) in **1** confirms the presence of two diastereotopic protons, axial and equatorial.

Notably, ¹H NMR spectral resonances (CD₃CN; 298 K) of [(η^6 -C₆H₆)Ru(L¹⁰)](PF₆) (**2**) in general and aromatic ring

protons of ligand L¹⁰(-) in particular were not resolved (see below). In fact, the spectral feature at lower temperatures (253 and 233 K) is very different from that of room temperature (298 K). In **2**, the expected singlet resonance for the coordinated benzene at 298 K is replaced by two singlet signals at lower temperature (233 K), consistent with the presence of benzene-coordinated Ru^{II} and the existence of two diastereomers^{3i,11,13a,20}. Fig. 3 displays partial ¹H NMR spectral feature of **2** at various temperatures, attesting the coordination of the ligand L¹⁰(-) and the formation of half-sandwich complex. The observed low temperature spectrum (233 K) is well-resolved with expected splitting pattern of various aromatic and -CH₂- protons. The ¹H NMR spectrum at 233 K reveals the presence of two sets of signals for each proton. The proton resonances were assigned, based on available ¹H NMR spectral pattern for (HL¹⁰)¹⁶, closely similar half-sandwich complexes reported by us [(η^6 -C₆H₆)Ru(L⁹)](PF₆)¹¹ (HL⁹, 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-[[2'-(pyridin-2-yl)benzylamino)methyl]-phenol) and associated coupling constant. The signals corresponding to pyridyl and phenolate ring protons

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum (400 MHz) of [(η^6 -C₆H₆)Ru(L⁶)](PF₆) (**1**) in CD₃CN at 298 K (solvent and water peaks marked by S and *, respectively).

Fig. 3. Part of the variable-temperature ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**) in CD_3CN (δ values in ppm).

and methylene protons at 298 K are intrigued by the spectral feature at 253 K. While at 253 K two sets of broad signals appear but the splitting of the signals for the pyridyl ring protons and that of $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups is not observed. However, on further cooling down to 233 K, these two set of signals become sharp and expected splitting pattern is also observed (Fig. 3). The ^1H NMR spectral results clearly indicate that complex **2** exhibits fluxional behaviour. It is likely that the dynamic ^1H NMR behaviour is due to the fast interchange of two diastereomers^{12b}, which may arise due to coordination by the asymmetric (three different donor groups) $\text{L}^{10}(-)$, the Ru centre assumes a chiral center and in turn the central tertiary amine nitrogen also becomes chiral. The interchange of two diastereomers may be possible because of fluxionality associated with $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\}^{2+}$ moiety and weak binding of the amine nitrogen to Ru^{II} . The ^1H NMR spectrum of **2** in CD_3COCD_3 (298 K) shows similar behaviour, as observed in

CD_3CN . Therefore, the possibility where the ligand might be undergoing a tridentate \rightleftharpoons bidentate interconversion due to weak bonding by amine nitrogen with a solvent molecule reversibly entering the coordination sphere of ruthenium is less probable.

In contrast to previously reported half-sandwich complexes of closely similar ligands¹² the ^1H NMR spectral behaviour reveals that complex **2** was isolated as a mixture of two diastereomers. As the main difference is the absence of substituents (bulky *tert*-butyl group in $\text{L}^9(-)$ or a polar nitro group in $\text{L}^7(-)$) at the phenolate ring in $\text{L}^{10}(-)$ from the previous report, we are inclined to believe that the driving force for the diastereospecificity in the synthesis of previously reported complexes is either due to the formation of strong hydrogen-bonds in the case of nitro-substituted ligand $\text{L}^7(-)$ or steric hindrance of bulky *tert*-butyl groups in other three complexes¹¹.

In essence, while the ^1H NMR spectral results of **1** clearly indicate that the solid state structure (*vide infra*) is retained in solution, for **2** it indicates the coexistence and rapid inter-change of two diastereomers in solution.

*Molecular structures of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**):*

In order to confirm the identity of the cations in **1** and **2**, coordinated by phenolate-based tridentate ligands $\text{L}^6(-)$ and $\text{L}^{10}(-)$, crystal structure analyses were undertaken. X-Ray crystallographic analyses confirm the structure of the complexes **1** and **2** (Fig. 4, Table 2). The cations exhibit the expected and usual pseudo-octahedral half-sandwich 'piano-

Fig. 4. Perspective views of the metal coordination environment in (a) $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (complex **1**) (CCDC No. 753757) and (b) $(R_{\text{Ru}}, S_{\text{N}})-[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (complex **2**) (CCDC No. 753758). Hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles ($^\circ$) for $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**)

	1	2
Ru(1)–N(1)	2.141(6)	2.076(3)
Ru(1)–N(2)	–	2.207(3)
Ru(1)–O(1)	2.011(8)	2.059(3)
Ru(1)–C(1)	2.195(7)	2.178(4)
Ru(1)–C(2)	2.177(7)	2.197(4)
Ru(1)–C(3)	2.175(7)	2.200(4)
Ru(1)–C(4)	–	2.195(4)
Ru(1)–C(5)	–	2.190(4)
Ru(1)–C(6)	–	2.185(4)
C(1)–C(2)	1.443(10)	1.409(6)
C(2)–C(3)	1.380(11)	1.397(6)
C(1)–C(1) ^a	1.374(14)	–
C(3)–C(3) ^a	1.463(18)	–
C(3)–C(4)	–	1.420(6)
C(4)–C(5)	–	1.394(6)
C(5)–C(6)	–	1.414(6)
C(1)–C(6)	–	1.389(6)
N(1)–Ru(1)–N(1) ^a	88.8(3)	–
N(1)–Ru(1)–O(1)	87.7(2)	84.66(11)
N(1)–Ru(1)–N(2)	–	78.48(11)
N(2)–Ru(1)–O(1)	–	87.07(11)

^aSymmetry generated atom.

stool' disposition around the Ru^{II} ion^{9–11} with the benzene ligand occupying one face of the octahedron (the ruthenium atom is π bonded to the $\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6$ group) and the coordination of the two pyrazoles N1 and N1* (complex **1**), and pyridine and amine N1 and N2 (complex **2**), and a phenolate O1 on the other face. The N–Ru–N angles have values of 88.8(3) $^\circ$ (**1**) and 78.48(11) $^\circ$ (**2**), deviated from 90 $^\circ$ as per demand of the bite of the ligand, for a facial coordination. The bite angle is less (78.48 $^\circ$), when (2-pyridyl)alkylamine arm is forming a five-membered chelate ring ($\text{L}^6(-)$ in **1**), and it is close to 90 $^\circ$ (88.8 $^\circ$), when two pyrazoles are attached to 2- and 6-positions of the phenolate ring by methylene spacers, are forming two seven-membered chelate ring ($\text{L}^{10}(-)$ in **2**). The N–Ru–O angles are 87.7(2) $^\circ$ (**1**) and 84.66(11) $^\circ$ (**2**) are also deviated due to ligand bite angle. The bite angle is larger in **1**, when two N-donors and an O-donor are forming seven-membered chelate ring and it is smaller [84.66(11) $^\circ$ (**2**)], when they are forming a six-membered chelate ring.

In **1**, the two pyrazole and the phenolate ring of $\text{L}^6(-)$ are each planar; however, the pyrazole mean plane is tilted to

the other pyrazole ring and phenolate ring at an angle of 67.6° and 80.8°, respectively, attesting its nonplanarity. The pyridyl and phenolate ring of L¹⁰(-) in **2** are each planar however, the pyridine mean plane is tilted to the phenolate ring at an angle of 34.9°, revealing its nonplanarity.

For complexes **1** and **2** the observed trend in Ru–C, Ru–N(py), Ru–N(pz), Ru–N(amine) and Ru–O(phenolate) distances, reflecting mutual *trans* influence, is a consequence of interplay between the steric and electronic factors associated with coordinating ability of tridentate ligands L⁶(-) and L¹⁰(-), in a closely similar metal coordination environment.

Interestingly, X-ray structural analyses revealed noticeable differences in the bonding interactions (metric parameters) of tridentate ligands L⁶(-) and L¹⁰(-) and also the characteristics of π -bonded benzene rings in these cations (Table 2 and Table 3). From a careful look at the metric parameters of Table 3, which lists pertinent bonding parameters for the

bond is 2.195(7) Å (the other Ru–C bonds are 2.175(7) and 2.177(7) Å) is *trans* to phenolate O atom of L¹(-). Thus in **1**, the extent of *trans* influence follows the order: phenolate > pyrazole. In **2**, the longest Ru–C bond 2.200(4) Å (the other Ru–C bonds are 2.178(4) and 2.197(4) Å) is *trans* to pyridine N atom and the shortest Ru–C bond of 2.178(4) Å is *trans* to amine N of L¹⁰(-). Here the extent of *trans* influence follows the order: pyridine > phenolate > amine. This trend could be rationalized if we take into account the fact that between the π -acceptor and the σ -donors, the former has greater *trans* influence than the σ -donor. Moreover, among the σ -donors, better σ -donor has greater *trans* influence. The greater *trans* influence of pyridine is thus understandable. The O(phenolate) carrying negative charge is better σ -donor, thus its greater *trans* influence than pyrazole N in **1** and amine N in **2** is also understandable. The shortest Ru–C₆H₆ centroid distance (Table 3) in **1** clearly reveals that between phenolate-based ligands present in **1** and **2** the ligand L⁶(-) provides maximum relative strength of $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\}^{2+}$ unit.

Average Ru–C distances in **1** (Table 3) are comparable to that reported in similar three-legged ‘piano-stool’ complexes, including $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{Cl}\}^+$ unit^{9–11}. The Ru–N(pz) bond lengths observed in **1** compare well with the values found in similar three-legged piano-stool complexes with N-donor ligands^{9l,o,10b,11}. The Ru–O distances are comparable to that reported in the literature for closely similar complexes^{3d,g,11,13a,b}.

Non-covalent interaction:

The existence of non-covalent interactions^{21,22} and particularly C–H...O interactions^{6d,10d,22–24} have been identified in organometallic molecules, including half-sandwich complexes having $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\}^{2+}$ moiety. From this background and our own activity in this field^{10b,c,24} we wished to identify primarily C–H...O interactions in **1** and **2**.

A closer inspection of the crystal packing diagrams of **1** and **2** reveals that these organometallic molecules are engaged in secondary (non-covalent) interactions (see below). Relevant bond distances, bond angles, and symmetry are summarized in Table 4. The C–H...O hydrogen-bonding parameters observed in this work are in good agreement with literature tabulations, including our own findings^{10c,23,24}. In **1**, the oxygen atom O(1) of phenolate is involved in hydrogen-bonding to one of the hydrogen atoms H(12B) of the methyl group present at the *para* position of phenolate ring

Table 3. Summary of relevant bond distances (Å) for $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)$ (**1**) and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**2**)

	1	2
Av Ru–C	2.195(7)	2.1908(4)
Ru–C ₆ H ₆ (centroid)	1.662	1.681
Av C–C	1.4138(12)	1.4038(6)
Ru–N _{py}	–	2.076(3)
Ru–N _{amine}	–	2.207(3)
Ru–N _(pz)	2.141(6)	–
Ru–O _{phenolate}	2.011(8)	2.059(3)

complexes **1** and **2**, the following generalizations emerge. (i) The Ru–O(phenolate) bond is stronger in complex **1** [2.011(8) Å] than in **2** [2.096(4) Å]. It is understandable given the fact that in L⁶(-) an electron releasing methyl group is present at the *para* position of the phenolate ring. (ii) Within the present group of complexes **1** and **2**, phenolate O binds most effectively in both and the least effective binding is observed for N(amine) in **2**, by the ligand L¹⁰(-). (iii) The Ru–N(py) bond in complex **2** is stronger than Ru–N(amine) bond and is weaker than Ru–O(phenolate) bond. This trend is understandable, given the fact that the O(phenolate) is deprotonated and carries a negative charge. Hence it forms a strong σ -bond with Ru^{II} and pyridine is a better π -acceptor so it binds more effectively than the amine (Table 3). (iv) In **1** and **2**, the distortion at the coordinated benzene ligand is present, with respect to the Ru–C bond distances. In **1** the longest Ru–C

of $L^6(-)$ from a neighbouring molecule, leading to the formation of 1D hydrogen-bonded chain (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. View of the formation of the unimolecular 1D chain through C–H...O hydrogen-bonding in $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^6)]^+$ unit in **1**. All the hydrogen atoms except those involved in hydrogen bonding have been omitted for clarity.

In **2**, weak C–H...O hydrogen-bonds and C–H... π interactions^{24c,25,26} are observed. Unlike linear assembly observed in the structures of **1**, complex **2** self-assembles via intermolecular C–H...O/ π interactions into supramolecular wheel-like structure. The extended bifurcated C–H...O interactions involving H10 of pyridine and H12B of methylene with Ru^{II}-coordinated phenolate O1 leads to the formation of wheel-like structure (Fig. 6; Table 4). In addition to C–H...O interactions, **2** is engaged in two types of C–H... π interactions, involving C23–H23 of phenolate ring with the dangling phenyl ring of benzyl group of $L^{10}(-)$ of neighbouring molecule and C26–H26 of phenolate ring with the phenolate ring of $L^{10}(-)$ of neighbouring molecule (C23–H23... Ct (phenyl ring centroid) distance: 2.562 Å; C2...Ct distance: 3.5112 Å; C–H...C_t angle, $\theta = 145^\circ$ and C26–H26...Ct (phenolate ring

Fig. 6. (a) A view of the part of “molecular wheel” showing C–H...O hydrogen-bonding interactions. (b) A view of C–H... π interaction involving C_6H_6 ring of the dangling benzyl arm and phenolate ring of $L^{10}(-)$. (c) A perspective view of the formation of a “molecular wheel” (Cyclic hexamer) through C–H...O hydrogen bonding of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})]^+$ unit in **2**. All the hydrogen atoms except those involved in hydrogen bonding and C–H... π interaction have been omitted for clarity.

Table 4. Hydrogen-bonding (C–H \cdots O/ π) parameters for $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^6)]^+$ in **1** and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})]^+$ in **2**

$D - \text{H} \cdots A$	$\text{H} \cdots A, \text{ \AA}$	$D \cdots A, \text{ \AA}$	$D - \text{H} \cdots A$
$[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^6)]^{1+}$	unit in 1		
C12–H12B \cdots O1	2.513 ^[i]	3.4205(3) ^[i]	140.6 ^{o[iii]}
$[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{10})]^{1+}$	unit in 2		
C10–H10 \cdots O1	2.357 ^[iv]	3.3271(1) ^[iv]	148.2 ^{o[v]}
C12–H12A \cdots O1	2.518 ^[iv]	3.4615(1) ^[iv]	144.9 ^{o[v]}
C23–H23 \cdots Ct1	2.562 ^[vi]	3.5112(1) ^[vi]	145.8 ^{o[vi]}
C26–H26 \cdots Ct2	2.439 ^[vii]	3.4918(1) ^[vii]	163.5 ^{o[vii]}
(i) $-1 + x, y, z$. (ii) $1 + x, y, z$. (iii) $1 + x, 1 + y, z$. (iv) $-1 + x, 1 + y, z$. (v) $2 - x, 1 - y, 1 - z$. (vi) $y, 1 - x + y, -z$. (vii) $1 + x - y, x, -z$. (viii) $y, 1 - x + y, -z$. (ix) $1 + x - y, x, -z$.			

centroid) distance: 2.439 Å; C2 \cdots Ct distance: 3.4918 Å; C–H \cdots C_t angle, $\theta = 163^\circ$] (Fig. 4; Table 4).

Conclusion

Several examples have been reported in the literature of structurally characterized mononuclear three-legged half-sandwich complexes of type $\{(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L})\}^{1+}$ (L is a uninegative tridentate ligand), few systematic studies have been made to design this class of half-sandwich complexes with the intention of pinpointing critical roles that the ancillary ligands play in fine-tuning structure-bonding properties of these organometallic molecules. Despite a few examples of structurally characterized 'piano-stool' half-sandwich complexes of type $\{[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L})]^{1+}$ [L = mononegative salicylaldehyde-based Schiff base ligand (only one example with reduced Schiff base ligand)], no report is available in the literature on systematic studies of similar complexes with use of (2-pyridyl)alkylamine-phenolate-based tridentate non-Schiff base ligand. In this work we have provided two such examples. Notably, due to coordination by one of the ligands the Ru^{II} centre becomes chiral and in turn the central tertiary amine nitrogen also becomes chiral. The ¹H NMR spectra of $\{[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)\}^+$ **2** exhibit two sets of signals at 233 K (fluxional behavior), due to the fast interchange of two diastereomers. The two ligands used in this work carry sites suitable for linking molecules preferentially through non-covalent interactions. In fact, careful analysis of crystal-packing diagrams of both complexes the presence of non-covalent interactions (C–H \cdots O) is revealed. Studies on proof-of-concept of the ligand L⁶(–) coordinating to a first-transition series ion utilizing all three donor sites are currently under-

way and the outcome of such an investigation will be published elsewhere.

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Supplementary data

Crystallographic data of the complexes $\{[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^6)](\text{PF}_6)\}^+$ and $\{[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{10})](\text{PF}_6)\}^+$ have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC numbers 753757 and 753758, respectively.

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